

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FAGAN****FIRST NAME: GREGORY****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied X US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author X did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author X did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: **Microsoft® Word for Microsoft 365 on Windows 10**

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In 1919, the *Journal of the American Medical Association (JAMA)* published C. St. Clair Drake's manuscript entitled "The Influence of the War on Preventive Medicine and Public Health." Which of the below choices best exemplifies correct Turabian-style paraphrasing of the following original passage?

The greatest changes in health development, however, will come out of the tremendous interest in public service created during the war and which found expression in the upbuilding of many large extragovernmental organizations engaged in various phases of patriotic and philanthropic work. (Drake 1919)

- Drake (1919) predicted that advances in public health would arise from the war effort, which saw the establishment of large non-governmental organizations committed to philanthropic causes. ¹**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers.*, 9th ed. (Chicago, Ill: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 135–38.

- Changes in health development will come out of the interest in public service created during the war and which found expression in the upbuilding of large extragovernmental organizations engaged in various phases of patriotic and philanthropic work.
 - Changes in health development will come out of the interest in public service created during the war and which found expression in the upbuilding of many large extragovernmental organizations engaged in various phases of patriotic and philanthropic work (Drake 1919).
 - Advances in public health would arise from the war effort, which “saw the establishment of large non-governmental organizations committed to philanthropic causes”.
2. Kate Turabian's (2018) *Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* outlines which two citation styles?
- author-date style and notes-bibliography style** ²
 - book-date style and title-bibliography style
 - author-time style and notes-citation style
 - title-date style and title-bibliography style
3. Which of the following defines a primary source?

² Ibid., 240.

- Shows original ideas, reports on fresh discoveries, or spreads new information and are the considered the raw supporting evidence** ³
 - Consists of data or information gleaned through the work of others and can be considered the literature of a field.
 - Summarizes or repackages ideas or other information based on a collection of
 - Describes, discusses, interprets, analyzes, evaluates, summarizes, and processes primary information.
4. According to Bloomberg and Volpe's (2016), *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation a Roadmap from Beginning to End*, what does triangulation refer to?
- The use of multiple methods or data sources to develop a comprehensive understanding of phenomena*** ⁴
 - Is the ability to comprehend and articulate a problem from the viewpoint of individuals experiencing it.
 - Is a three-part structured interview technique consisting of a series of ten open questions
 - A stratified sampling technique that divides a population into subpopulations that may differ in at least three critical ways.
5. In qualitative research methodology, what is the purpose of Grounded Theory?

³ Ibid., 53.

⁴ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End. 4th Ed.*, 4th ed. (Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, 2016), 258

- To inductively generate theory that is grounded in, or emerges from, the data.⁵
- To deductively generate theory based solely on participant observations.
- Analyzing the social context in which the communication between the researcher and the respondent occurred.
- A technique used to validate data and control for statistical outliers.
6. Which statement is correct regarding parenthetical citations?
- A parenthetical citation is put at the end of the sentence or clause that contains the quotation or other information. If the author's name is mentioned in the text, the citation (in parentheses) is put right after the author's name.⁶
- A parenthetical citation is typically used to provide contradictory information to round out an argument
- Parenthetical citations are only applicable in quantitative research methods.
- Parenthetical citations are different than in-text citations.
7. A mixed-methods design is advantages because it?
- is a distinct and complex research approach that intentionally and systematically uses both qualitative and quantitative approaches and methods concurrently in one study, or sequentially in two or more studies.⁷
- removes all biases and sampling and data limitations.

⁵ Ibid., 171.

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 397.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 136

- allows for both quantitative and qualitative data to be analysed and presented separately.
 - is only used in the life sciences.
8. Which one of the following is true about tertiary sources?
- Tertiary sources are books and articles that synthesize secondary sources for general readers.** ⁸
 - Tertiary sources provide original insights and analyses.
 - Tertiary sources are essential to scientific and educational communities.
 - Tertiary sources are raw data that have not been processed.
9. According to Bloomberg and Volpe (2016), a literature review is:
- a summative description of the contents of articles and books.
 - a series of isolated summaries of previous studies
 - a type of research that evaluates, critiques, and synthesizes representative literature on a subject.** ⁹
 - a detailed bibliography of all works on a given subject and includes primary, secondary, and tertiary sources of information.
10. According to the World Health Organization's (WHO) second edition style manual, WHO terminology for diseases and medical terms are based on:

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 55.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 352.

- The WHO's International Classification of Diseases (ICD) criteria, which is a globally used diagnostic tool for epidemiology, health management and clinical purposes.
- International Nomenclature of Diseases (IND) from the *Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS)*.**¹⁰
- Free-text entry from treating physicians, which is used to account for significant variations in disease nomenclature.
- Pharmaceutical and medical device company expertise and categorization.

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, 2nd ed. (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 10.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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